

THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN PEACE BUILDING IN POLITICS AND ECONOMY

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Abstract

This paper addresses the role of women in peace building, politics and economy with emphasis on the Nigerian context. Just like in most African communities, in Nigeria women are relegated to the background. They are not seen to be contributing or playing any significant roles to the development of their community or the nation at large. The women are always confined to the domestic roles by the society, as if they are incapable of going beyond that. Hence, this paper seeks to provide some evidence of how women have played and are playing their roles in peace building, politics and the nation's economic development. The paper also highlights that despite the roles played by women, there are they encounter numerous hurdles. One of the main challenges they face is that they are not given enough freedom to operate their activities, hence, limiting their impact. The paper concludes by restating that women should be appreciated and acknowledged by the society in their contributions and roles to the development of their community and the nation.

Introduction

In this paper, I reflect on the interface of peace building, politics and economic development, focusing on how women in Nigeria contribute in these three areas. Putting them together is a great task to be done. For this reason, in this paper, I have interwoven them together to enable them interact with one another. It is beyond this paper to go at great length with each key word as given on the title.

Subjugation of women, in fact, is a symptom of man's fallen nature. If the work of Christ involves the breaking of the entail [inherited consequences] of the fall, the implication of his work for the liberation of women is plain. Unwarranted assumptions have sometimes been drawn from the fact that all twelve of the original apostles were men. But in fact our Lord's male disciples cut a sorry figure alongside his female disciples, especially in his last hours; and it was to women that he first entrusted the privilege of carrying the news of his resurrection. He treated women in a completely natural and unselfconscious way as real persons. He imparted his teaching to the eager

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bridging divides in regions affected by violence. These organizations among others: Women Empowerment Education and Peace Building Initiative (WEPBI), this group focuses mainly on humanitarian needs and sustainable peace building in communities. Women's Consortium of Nigeria (WOCON), this group dedicated themselves to the enforcement of rights, equality, and peace in every society. Women's Interfaith Council (WIC) focuses mainly or uses interfaith dialogue to build peace among the society where there is conflict. Women Peace-building Council (WPC) was inaugurated in 2020 with the purpose of promoting women's involvement in peace-building. Peace building is an inclusive democratic process that requires a close partnership, respect and dialogue among all stakeholders - including the ordinary citizens. It is the effort to promote human security in societies marked by violence and conflict.⁴ The overarching goal of peace building is to strengthen the capacity of societies to manage conflict without any recourse to violence, as a means to achieve sustainable human security and reconciliation in societies. Positive peace brings transformation in the society. It helps the citizens to achieve freedom and establishes equality of male and female in all spheres of human lives.⁵ When it comes to Capacity Building, Search for Common Ground Nigeria (SCGN) in their 8th March reports 2026 clearly reported that, in 2025, 871 women were trained as mediators, and over 6,000 women engaged in active peace-building initiatives. The restoration of democracy and conflict transformation in Nigeria confirm the fact that the power of powerless is expressed fully through non-violent means of politics by solidarity, purposeful communication and collective action. This means expansion of the participation of women at all levels of society and every aspect of public life is a way to make politics human, non-violent and peaceful. This has been the cry of Nigerian women since the dawn of human civilization. It is a cry of the majority of the Nigerian population for building an order in society so that stakes for peace become a common concern for all members- women, men, children and disabled. Exclusion of women in the politics of peace means paralyzing more than half of the population from creative change and making the change sustainable.⁶

Violent conflict affects all the citizens; especially the weaker sections of the society like women, children, the disabled and the poor. They lack sufficient mechanisms for security, safety and protection. They are the ones who are the direct victim of various kinds of conflicts, direct, structural and cultural. Even though the cost of the conflict is borne by these sections of the society, the benefits are shared and taken by the powerful actors and stakeholders. mostly men. Therefore, the situation of conflict must be removed through democratization of the state, political parties, civil society, economic institutions and also the community themselves. This is only possible when the collective voice of women is expressed in the public sphere and long-term realistic planning of society is made.⁷ Peace requires truth telling about the condition where political leaders conservatively maintain a creek between the promise and practice and ultimately fail to recognize the core meaning of politics which is to maintain morality in public life and not to lie to the people.⁸ Women's organizations in Nigeria are struggling hard

⁴ A. A. Jekayinfa. *Journal of Educational Theory and Practice*. 5 (1&2), 1999. THE ROLE OF NIGERIAN WOMEN IN CULTURE AND NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT.

⁵ A. A. Jekayinfa. *Journal of Educational Theory and Practice*. 5 (1&2), 1999. THE ROLE OF NIGERIAN WOMEN IN CULTURE AND NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT.

⁶ Samira Paudel, Women's Role in Peace Building in Nigeria accessed 5/3/2026

⁷ Samira Paudel, Women's Role in Peace Building in Nigeria accessed 22/02/2026

⁸ Samira Paudel, Women's Role in Peace Building in Nigeria accessed 22/02/2026

to minimize the level of violence in politics and seeking for legitimate roles in peace negotiation, mediation and in the conflict resolution process.

Socio-Political and Economic Roles for Women in Africa

The real meaning of politics is to serve public interest, exercise justice and set up a cordial relationship between the political actors and stakeholders of the society. It should provide essential education for right conduct and talk about the freedom of all men and women. Proper education, teaching and socialization try to minimize the use of violent words in personal and public communication and action in daily life .⁹

While all women around the world share many social struggles, one must not lose sight of the fact that strong differences exist between them. This is where problems arise when any group of women purports to speak for and on behalf of others simply because they are all women. Whereas there are marked differences from location to location, western feminist theory has historically privileged gender over issues of race and economic location, both of which are of paramount importance in any discussion on women in Africa.

Debates on women's issues have in the last few decades assumed prominence on the global agenda. Issues concerning women are topics of meetings and conferences around the world. Legislation on how to improve the lot of women is constantly being introduced and passed. This is a good development. There seems to be general agreement on the fact that in all human societies, including Plato's, women are not treated as equals of men. It is against the backdrop of this consensus that these debates were generally received as timely and welcome. To meaningfully carry on the discussions, women's voices needed to be heard and included. Unfortunately, not all women had equal access to avenues that made this possible. Voices heard were generally from one part of the world, the west.¹⁰ These voices purported to speak for all women irrespective of location. While they did a good job from the limited perspective of their own experiences, a lot of misrepresentation arose due to their lack of knowledge on the lived experiences of those they purported to represent.

Nigerian women as a group, make up about half of the national population. They contribute significantly to the national economy although this contribution is not fully acknowledged because the majority operates within the informal sector that is difficult to calibrate on "received" economic terms. Many are farmers. A large number are involved in distributive trade, while several engage in cross-border trading. Whatever their occupation, women tend to form supportive organizations through which they protect their interests. Market women are a very good example. On the political scene, stories and legends abound of powerful Nigerian women who exerted great influence in their time.¹¹ Unfortunately, contemporary Nigerian women, like the men, are struggling to find their feet in the general confusion that defines politics in the country today. Despite political problems, Nigerians continue to be a proud people, difficult to repress. During the prolonged period of military rule, Nigerians learnt to lead their lives "in spite" of the state.

⁹ Samira Paudel, Women's Role in Peace Building in Nigeria accessed 22/02/2026

¹⁰ Ufomata, Titi. (2000). WOMEN IN AFRICA: THEIR SOCIO-POLITICAL AND ECONOMIC ROLES. *West Africa Review*: 2 , 1. [iucode: <http://www.icaap.org/iucode?101.2.1.4>]. Accessed 23/02/2026

¹¹ Ufomata, Titi. (2000). WOMEN IN AFRICA: THEIR SOCIO-POLITICAL AND CONOMIC ROLES. *West Africa Review*: 2 , 1. [iucode: <http://www.icaap.org/iucode?101.2.1.4>]. Accessed 23/02/2026

Women and Politics in Nigeria

Over the years, there has been raging debates over the participation or desire of women in Nigerian politics. Some argue that: Women are regarded as weaker sexes are social constructs owing to social value, norms and beliefs, which have neglected their meaningful contributions and have placed them in a subordinate position to men in the nation's political system. This 'sexual division of labour' in the political system is often traced to the onset of colonialism in Nigeria. Their Western cultural notion of male superiority reflected in their relations with Nigerians. The political enfranchisement of women in Nigerian politics seems to have maintained on the surface a level of gender equity politically, because it is assumed that constitutionally there are no barriers to women's participation. But what exactly is/are the problems and prospects women encounter in their quest to participate in politics? Women movements can be said to have been largely responsible for an increase in women's political participation. Kira Sanbonmatsu recognized an important variable responsible for the increase in women participation other than women movements. In her study, she concluded that "women would be even more supportive of electing more women to public office if they were knowledgeable as men about the extent of women's under representation" (Sanbonmatsu 2003:367).

Discussing women's role politically, it could be safely said that Nigerian women have contributed significantly to the growth of the nation. It is not an exaggeration to affirm that women played prominent and decisive roles in the socio-political history and decision-making processes of their respective traditional societies. In pre-colonial Nigeria, through their selfless sacrifices and gallantry, they served as catalysts for brokering peace during crises (in their local communities there were inter-mariages between villages/tribes which helped in brokering peace by the women they married. They brokered peace in local politics and economy). Painfully though, despite the prominent roles played by these women, the involvement of women in the political system in Nigeria is yet to be remarkable for any observable appreciative respite for the women folk.

Survey of Women's Participation

The 1979 Nigerian constitution guaranteed the rights of women to participate in active politics; however, the last decade has witnessed a relative increase in women's participation. This is only when we measure increase in participation with certain standards like the number of women who vote in elections; the number of public offices held by women; number of women related policies implemented by government etc. Over the years, there has been a remarkable increase in women's participation in politics in Nigeria considering these standards, yet there is inherently a pronounced level of under-representation of women in politics when compared with their male counterparts. Women's aspiration to participate in governance is premised on the following ground; that women in Nigeria represent half of the population and hence should be allowed a fair share in decision-making and the governance of the country. Secondly that all human beings are equal and women possess the same rights as men to participate in governance and public life. The right to democratic governance is an entitlement conferred upon all citizens by law. The 1999 Nigerian constitution by virtue of Section 40 states the following: Every person shall be entitled to assemble freely and associate with other persons, and in particular he may form or belong to any political party, trade union or any other association for the protection of his interests: From the foregoing, it appears that there is nothing in the constitution, which excludes the participation of women in politics in Nigeria. Yet when it comes to actual practice, there is extensive discrimination. Though concerted efforts have been made by government and non-governmental organizations to increase the level of participation of women in politics in the line with the declaration made at the fourth World Conference on women in Beijing, which advocated 30% affirmative action, few and almost insignificant number of women were elected into various posts in the 1999, 2003, 2007, 2011 and 2015 general elections held in the country.

Female representation in the Nigerian National Assembly (2015–2025) remains under 7%, significantly lower than regional averages, with women occupying 20 or fewer seats out of 469 (4.3%–6.5%) in the 8th, 9th, and 10th assemblies. Key figures show a decline from 29 women (2015) to 20 or fewer in 2023, facing structural barriers. 10th Assembly (2023–2025): Approximately 20 female lawmakers (4 senators, 16 in the House of Representatives). Other sources indicate even lower numbers of 3 females in the Senate.

9th Assembly (2019-2023): Only 21 women out of 469 members, accounting for roughly 4.5% of the total, with a significant reduction from previous terms.

8th Assembly (2015-2019): Approximately 29 women (6.2%) held seats, representing a continuous trend of under-representation.

Overall Average: Studies highlight an average of about 5%–6.7% women in the assembly, far below the African regional average of 23.4%.¹²

Men dominate most public offices till date. When women are given their proper place, their roles to play could be seen vividly and appreciated. It is only in few places that one could see women given a place to play their role. Such examples are Plateau and Lagos States that had their Deputy Governors as Women, there are a handful in the National Assembly because it is just 5.6 percent of members of the House of Representative and 6.5 percent of the Senators. Also with the nineteen years of uninterrupted democratic governance (1999-2022), Nigeria is yet to produce a female governor in any of the 36 states of the Federation.

Why Few Women Participate in Politics:

A. Patriarchal System and Gender

This system does not allow women to play their roles properly in the society. The family is the main institution of patriarchy (Kate Millet, 1970), which is an important concept in explaining gender inequality. Literarily, it means “the rule of the father”; more broadly, it refers to a society ruled and dominated by men over women. This is inherent in most African families. Giving men a higher social status over females has crept into public life, which reflects in state activities. The family plays an important role in maintaining this patriarchal order across generations. The socialization of children to expect and accept different roles in life has created a social mechanism for the development of values that engender the several forms of discrimination against the female sex. The greatest psychological weapon available to man is the length of time they have enjoyed dominance over women, who have taken it for granted especially in politics that often continue to stereotype women and justify their subordination. This has made many women to believe that the ideal leadership must be from men and not from women. This is why horizontal violence is common among women as they see themselves as not capable to hold any influential position.

B. Women’s Views on Politics

Some consensus has been of the belief that Nigerian politics is based on high political willingness – those who have all it takes to compete in the turbulent environment; those who possess the ability to take it by force when force is required; those that can match violence with violence. This consensus belief that men possess the superiority strength, competitiveness, are self reliant and are prepared to tussle in political endeavour, whereas women are considered too passive to engage in politics and governance. This consensus is also constructed by societal norms and values, which through socialization has defined different gender roles according to biological differences. Women’s perception of politics as a dirty game and continued fright at the thought of violence has further alienated them from mainstream politics.

¹² statistics of Female Members of Nigerian National Assembly 2015-2025 pd Accessed 26/03/2026

In Nigeria, there seems to be no critical understanding of the difference between “a visible agenda for women and an impacting agenda for women.” (Nkoyo, 2002:29). While severally, emphasis is laid on women’s numerical strength, translating such into the attainment of power has been difficult as women are perceived as “supporters club, team of cheerers and clappers” in contrast to their male counterparts. Women politicians seek offices on the premise of being different; most believe they must do what men are doing to succeed. And the meekness of women is not to their advantage in political tussle.

C. Problem of Finance

Women’s historical experiences of discrimination puts them at a disadvantage economically. Over the years, sexual division of labour and job opportunities offered on sex basis has given men productive gender roles, enabling them to possess more purchasing power over their female counterparts. As a result, the Nigerian labour market has about 75% of labour being supplied by men. This economic disparity favours men to the disadvantage of women. Societal value assumes that peace building, economic development and political activities are masculine. Most success achieved by women in peace building, economic growth and politics has been through women movements that sponsor women aspirations financially and otherwise. Women’s dependence on men financially made manifest through wives’ dependence on their husbands in families reveals the extent of financial incapacitation of women in Nigeria. As a result, women aspirations in building the country have been grossly hampered by lack of financial bedrock to subsist their endeavour. Women have been pushed to the background for years; this has engendered a consciousness of women under- representation in public life. However, the intention of most women to participate in peace building is basically to support the nation, this is their substantive responsibility and it is even on this platform that most women emerge as public office holders successfully. They use the platform of women’s movement as a veritable platform to seize peace, economic and political power to consolidate the nation. For example, though women are in the minority, but when they moved a motion to contribute, they contribute responsibly and men honour their contribution especially in terms of peace initiative in the political parties and in economic development of the nation.

D. Cultural Factors

The customary practices of many contemporary societies are biased by subjugating women to men and undermining their self-esteem. The overall impact of gender bias, cultural norms and practices has entrenched a feeling of inferiority in women and place them at a disadvantage vis-a-vis their male counterpart in the socio-political scene even in urban centres. These socially constructed norms and stereotype roles make women overplay their ‘femininity’ by accepting that they are ‘weaker sexes’, overemphasizing the dainty nature of their sex and regarding exceptional achievement as masculine. For example, most customs often prefer sending the male child to school over the female, who is expected to nurture siblings and to be married off. This marginally increases the illiterate women and stiffens competition with their male counterparts in peace building, economic development and politics. With such a worldview, it is difficult for a woman to play her role as required.

Women’s Roles in Economic Development

Nigerian women are noted for their industry. Many of them are traders and farmers. They support their families economically. Most times, their contributions are trivialized and disregarded when in actual fact they bear the brunt of the families’ economic burden. The disadvantaged position of women in Nigeria started changing with acculturation. “Acculturation” is a process by which a minority individual or group tries to blend into the dominant society by taking on its cultural characteristics. Individuals who want to acculturate try to learn the dominant language, style of dress, patterns of behaviour, and other cultural characteristics so well that it is difficult to tell

that they are minority group members (Popenoe; 1991). Furthermore, Popenoe (1991) noted that it involves turning away from an ethnic heritage that may still carry emotional meaning and social connection.¹³

There was division of labour as men; women and children were assigned roles in the farms. Women also did the bulk of domestic chores and contributed extensively to the survival of the families and groups. Women's roles in employment, particularly in Nigeria could be categorized into agriculture, informal and formal sectors. Evidences from studies show that more women in the Eastern part of the country are involved in agriculture while the western states has more women participating in the informal sector and as for women in the Northern States their contributions are somehow hidden due to the widely practiced purdah system in that region which does not make them feasible like their male counterparts. The purdah problem has to do especially with some muslim women that are not allowed to work. But Christian women in Northern Nigeria are not affected by the purdah system. The Christian women work in different places be it private or public. For this reason, they contribute a lot to the economic development of the nation. Though, they are mostly engaged in the informal sector with their products hawked by their children and dependents.

Even though women's contribution in the formal sector is generally low, there has been a gradual increase in their numbers over the years. More worrisome is the fact that despite obvious increase in education, knowledge and skill of women, the modern world of employment is experiencing occupational segregation by sex. Women's quantitative increase in formal employment has not been matched by qualitative improvements in employment. Women are yet to break through the "glass ceiling". Indeed, they still form a minority in decision-making. Managerial positions, gender discrimination and unequal division of labour, such as in the sharing of family responsibilities, are still prevalent in most modern societies. Therefore, women's roles in economic development could be summarized in this way:

Many women are deeply involved in

- a) Production of black soap;
- b) Production of honey;
- c) In charge of day care and primary schools;
- d) Organization of literacy classes;
- e) Preservation of perishable food items;
- f) Promotion of Economic Policy Institute (EPI)
- (g) Promotion of sanitation programmes¹⁴

This is apart from the main work that they do in the public sector in different boards and parastatals. By these efforts of women, peace is achieved in homes/society because they extend their helping hands to their husbands, children, community, society and the nation at large. And they are always in fellowship with each other through forming cooperative support groups, sisters in business groups etc. Through this, they visit each other and have fellowship with their families which in turn brings unity in society.

¹³ Mrs. Josephine Nwagwu, *European Journal of Social Sciences – Volume 7, Number 4 (2009)*135

Acculturation and the Socio-Economic Development of the Post Independent African Woman; The Nigerian Example. Accessed 18/2/2026.

¹⁴ A. A. Jekayinfa. *Journal of Educational Theory and Practice*. 5 (1&2), 1999. THE ROLE OF NIGERIAN WOMEN IN CULTURE AND NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT.

Recommendations

Women suffer most in crisis situations. It is men who predominantly fight, and women stay behind to fend for families and communities. But they are neither consulted nor allowed to partake in decision-making. They are forced to bear the large part of the burden directly or indirectly. Therefore, it is not surprising that women are adopting strategies to play a prominent role in peace building process in Nigeria. Even if they are not coming in the forefront, there are still lots of things they have to work on to make personal, family, society and life of the nation violence-free. The agencies of socialization such as media, schools, colleges and universities and political parties have to be re-educated so that the violent outcomes are made illegal by playing a vital role to stop the absurdity of the Nigerian society.¹⁵ There is also a need to eradicate the discriminatory nature of knowledge, institutions, laws and traditions that go against the empowerment of women. The virus of democratic politics should be spread into all levels of society from the family to international community so that the nature of violence is contained, completely moderated and finally eliminated from the life of women and the society. There should also be an inter-subjective framework of economic, social and political participation of women so that the rationality of liberation guides the conduct of men and women in public and private lives. And finally, the realization of the system of rights and human dignity must be created for not just the equal opportunities but also equal outcome for men and women.

Unless the role of women is identified, the restraints of the past are addressed and the new possibilities of freedom, social justice and dignity and identity for both men and women are explored, inclusive peace is not possible for Nigeria. Once women get their legitimate role in the peace building process, they would become part of the ensuing governance structures. This is the right time for the citizens to take into account how to achieve inclusive peace whereby Nigerian women can become an actor rather than a factor in politics-the politics of decision-making about peace, peace keeping and peace building.

Conclusion

The issue of peace building is something that cannot be over-emphasized. Peace is needed in every strata of life, it is needed in development, politics and economic growth of the country at large. In this paper, we have seen the involvement of women in different sectors of life. Women have played great roles in peace building in politics and economic growth. Women speak on peace in media, conferences, seminars, stage rallies in schools and other programmes. But it became obvious from this paper that women are not given the avenue to play their roles in peace building, politics and economy as expected. The roles played by women in these sectors have been overshadowed by men because of the patriarchal system that operates in our society. There is need for the society to allow women to maximize their God given potentials. When this is done, there will be peace and tranquility in our society because women are peaceful by nature and they can give peace to the society and the country at large. This article should stimulate the larger society so that they can know and give women upper hand to in giving women the atmosphere they need to render their contribution in building the nation.

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¹⁵ Samira Paudel, Women's Role in Peace Building in Nigeria accessed 17/02/2026

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